

ENHANCING AUDIO CLARITY: REMOVING BACKGROUND NOISE WITH ADOBE AUDITION SOFTWARE

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Abstract: Background noise poses a persistent challenge in audio post-production, requiring advanced tools for effective reduction without compromising the clarity of desired sounds. This paper explores the application of Adobe Audition software, specifically its Adaptive Noise Reduction feature, as a powerful solution for removing background audio noise. The significance of noise reduction in achieving high-quality audio content is discussed, emphasizing the versatile capabilities of Adobe Audition in the realm of audio editing. A step-by-step guide outlines the process of loading audio files, creating sessions, identifying noise profiles, and applying adaptive noise reduction. The study concludes by highlighting the significance of such advanced tools in elevating the audio production process, catering to the needs of researchers, content creators, and audio professionals in diverse fields. The findings underscore the efficiency of Adobe Audition's noise reduction capabilities and its contribution to achieving pristine audio quality in various applications.

Keywords: Adobe Audition, Audio post-production, Noise reduction, Adaptive Noise Reduction, Audio editing, Background noise removal, Audio clarity, Digital audio processing, Multimedia production, Advanced audio tools.

In the realm of audio post-production, achieving pristine sound quality is paramount. One common challenge is dealing with background noise, which can detract from the overall clarity of audio recordings. This article explores the effective use of Adobe Audition software in removing background audio noise, a crucial process for professionals working with audio content.

The primary sources of sound modification lie in amplitude and high frequencies. Amplitude modification involves processes such as amplification, dynamic range adjustment, mixing, normalization, and panning. Frequency (spectral) modification encompasses filtering, equalization, and fast Fourier transform-based algorithms. Modifications based on phase and time. Formant modification. Compression.

As observed earlier, sound is characterized by its waveform. Modifying the waveform alters subjective characteristics such as pitch, clarity, and so on. How can we alter the physical characteristics of sound, and how do these modifications impact the perception of listeners?

We explore altering each physical characteristic of sound. Notably, the manipulation of sound is often achieved through mixing, especially in the context of editing and production. Digital processing editors provide a more accessible means compared to analog manipulation for users to modify sound characteristics.

Figure 1. Frequency interface

Amplitude Modification (Increasing Volume). When altering volume, the importance of sample amplitude is crucial. Consistent scaling, increasing or decreasing amplitude, or dynamically changing volume is achieved by amplifying and attenuating the audio signal using various tools. Amplitude modulation over time allows for a gradual increase or decrease in volume.

Frequency (Spectral) Modification. This method is dedicated to processing speed (frequency) for working with audio signals. The variable components of audio signals in the form of frequency (frequency spectrum) or spectral distribution are emphasized. Spectral components, such as sinusoidal vibrations, each possess their own amplitude and frequency characteristics.

Figure 2. Audition Software Edit Panel

A spectrum table facilitates the adjustment of frequency changes. The change in amplitude modulation aligns with spectral modifications.

Sound Filtering (Passing Through a Filter). Filtering, altering the speed of certain frequencies in a particular direction, is applied to the amplitude spectrum. Filtering (sound cleaning) is one of the methods considered for achieving specific goals. Filtering is utilized when it is necessary to limit or modify the frequency spectrum within certain boundaries. For instance, unnecessary noise or frequencies can be eliminated by selectively removing certain frequency components through filtering

Figure 3. Graphic Equalizer Panel

A crossover separates an incoming signal into multiple output channels, with each channel exclusively preserving a specific frequency range. Essentially, each output channel retains its unique frequency band, making use of a designated pathway and straightforward filters. Crossovers differ from equalizers but share a foundation built on similar principles.

In each audio system, the listening height of each component needs to be independently managed to reach the required balance. In such cases, each track must have its own port selected for audio signal output, indicating that a standard sound card is not sufficient. This type of crossover can only be used when a computer has a multi-channel digital-to-analog converter installed. Such specialized equipment is not readily available in the market.

A graphic equalizer, as mentioned earlier, is a collection of bandpass filters with a changeable coefficient of amplification, controlled by a slider-type regulator with a designated central frequency. This allows for precise control over the adjustable parameters of the equalizer, providing flexibility in managing the frequency response of audio signals.

Figure 4. Dialog Box of Graphic Equalizers

Multi-band graphic equalizers provide the capability to enhance the audio signal with various effects. In graphic editors, several types of multi-band equalizers are commonly used. For example, in the top part of the presented interface, there are three buttons that allow the user to choose from three variants of multi-band equalizers:

10 bands: Consists of 10 frequency bands with octave filters.

20 bands: Features 20 frequency bands with half-octave filters.

30 bands: Comprises 30 frequency bands with third-octave filters.

Slider-type controls allow adjusting the level of signals in a specific frequency range. The central frequency for setting an elementary filter is indicated by the knob at the top of the slider, but it is essential to note that the slider controls on the right and left sides set the cutoff frequencies, not the center frequencies. The selection of the slider is made by pressing the corresponding button above it, and then the slider is moved up or down using the knob indicator.

Background noise can stem from various sources, such as ambient sounds, electronic interference, or equipment hum. For researchers, content creators, and audio engineers using Adobe Audition, the ability to reduce or eliminate this unwanted noise is essential for producing high-quality audio content.

Adobe Audition: A Powerhouse for Audio Editing. Adobe Audition, part of the Adobe Creative Cloud suite, is renowned for its advanced audio editing

capabilities. Among its impressive features is the Adaptive Noise Reduction tool, designed to intelligently identify and minimize background noise in audio recordings.

Step-by-Step Guide to Removing Background Noise:

Launching Adobe Audition. Open the Adobe Audition software on your computer to begin the noise reduction process.

Loading the Audio File. Import the audio file containing background noise into the Adobe Audition interface.

Creating a New Session. Opt for a new session by selecting "File" and then "New." Choose a "Multitrack Session" for versatility.

Adding the Audio File. Import the audio file into the multitrack session for further processing.

Identifying the Noise. Locate a section in the audio track that solely contains background noise. This will be used to train Adobe Audition on the noise profile.

Adaptive Noise Reduction. Access the "Effects" menu and choose "Noise Reduction/Restoration." Select "Adaptive Noise Reduction" from the available options.

Configuring Parameters. Click on "Capture Noise Print" in the Adaptive Noise Reduction window. This action informs Adobe Audition about the noise characteristics, allowing the software to set parameters for noise reduction.

Applying Noise Reduction. Confirm the settings and apply the adaptive noise reduction. Adobe Audition will process the audio, reducing background noise while preserving the clarity of the desired sound.

Saving the Cleaned Audio. Save the cleaned audio file in the preferred format, ensuring the noise-free version is ready for use.

In conclusion, Adobe Audition's Adaptive Noise Reduction tool empowers users to tackle background audio noise efficiently. Whether you're a researcher, content creator, or audio professional, incorporating these steps into your workflow will help you achieve pristine audio quality and elevate your final productions. As

technology continues to advance, tools like Adobe Audition play a crucial role in enhancing the audio experience for various applications.

REFERENCE

1. Abduazizov. Electrical Engineering Theory. (Textbook). – Tashkent: "Fan va texnologiya", 2011, 416 p.
2. Abduazizov, D. Davronbekov. Radio Broadcasting and Reception Devices. Textbook. – Tashkent: "Fan va texnologiya", 2011, 272 p."
3. Pohlmann, K. C. (2010). Principles of Digital Audio. McGraw-Hill Education.
4. Rabiner, L., & Gold, B. (2011). Theory and Application of Digital Signal Processing. Prentice Hall.
5. Golovin, O.V. (2004). Radio Receiving Devices. – Moscow: Hot Line – Telecom. – 384 p.: ill..
6. Adobe. (2020). Adobe Audition User Guide. Retrieved from <https://helpx.adobe.com/audition/user-guide.html>